

Wadi Sarga Monastery

Secondary source

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* Secondary Source entry, prepared from a literature review by a Ph.D. RA

Entry tags: Christian, Middle Egypt, Religious Group, Monastery, Egypt, Monasticism, Religious Place

Wadi Sarga is located in Middle Egypt on the west bank of the Nile, c. 25km south of modern Asyut. Greek and Coptic texts dating from the 6th to 8th centuries suggest that the site was the location of a Monastery of Apa Thomas. Excavations were carried out between 1913 and 1914, but the results were never published in full due to the beginning of the First World War. The monastic settlement was developed in and around the existing pharaonic gallery quarries cut into the slopes of Wadi Sarga. The galleries were transformed into living quarters, while in a long gallery a 'Church cave' (or 'Rock Church') with an extensive painted program was created. The iconographic programme included haloed figures, busts of haloed saints, a depiction of John the Baptist and Zacharias and the Holy Spirit 'descending like a dove'. The scene of the Communion of the apostles has been represented on the half-dome of the apse. Other habitation sectors were constructed on the steep slopes of the 'gabal'. They were mainly mud-brick buildings, some supported by dry-stone construction foundations. A long, rectangular building (50m) has been described by Campbell Thompson as a 'stabl' or 'caravansserie', and was probably a place for the pack animals. At the mouth of the wadi, in and around the so-called vallum, was an apparently contemporary cemetery (Cemetery 1), with mud-brick lined grave-cuts containing badly preserved human remains. The archaeological and the textual evidence indicate that this was a flourishing and wealthy community that was involved in economic activities. The monks were in contact with the neighbouring monastic sites of Bawit and Deir el-Bala'izah. Unfortunately, nowadays Wadi Sarga is inaccessible because it has been converted into a military zone.

Date Range: 500 CE - 800 CE

Region: Upper Egypt: Asyut Region

Region tags: Africa, Northern Africa, Egypt

The region of Upper Egypt near the city of Asyut.

Status of Participants:

✓ Religious Specialists

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: O'Connell, E. R. 2014. R. Campbell Thompson's 1913/14 Excavation of Wadi Sarga and Other Sites. *British Museum Studies in Ancient Egypt and Sudan* 21: 121-192.
- Source 2: O'Connell, E. R. 2012. Settlements and Cemeteries of Late Antique Egypt. A Short History of Archaeological Collections in the British Museum. In M. Ayad (ed.) *Coptic Culture. Past, Present and*

Future: 102-103. Oxford.

– Source 3: Crum, W. E. and H. I. Bell (eds). 1922. Wadi Sarga: Coptic and Greek Texts from the Excavations Undertaken by the Byzantine Research Account. Copenhagen.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.trismegistos.org/place/2843>

– Source 1 Description: Trismegistos. An interdisciplinary portal of the ancient world

– Source 2 URL: <https://pleiades.stoa.org/places/756676>

– Source 2 Description: Pleiades. A a community-built gazetteer and graph of ancient places.

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1913-1914

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Byzantine Research Fund: Excavations at Wadi Sarga

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

Notes: Gabal

Type of elevation

– Hill

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

- ↳ Type of feature
 - Other [specify]: Quarry

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

- ↳ A single structure
 - No

- ↳ One single feature
 - Other [specify]: No single feature, but features as parts of structures.

- ↳ A group of structures:
 - Yes

- ↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:
 - No

Notes: The settlement was probably developed progressively

- ↳ A group of features:
 - Yes

- ↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:
 - No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Collapsed

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

–Other [specify]: No

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

– Natural phenomena

–Other [specify]: Abandoned and deteriorated due to natural decay.

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Apa Thomas

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Field doesn't know

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Field doesn't know

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– No

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

Notes: Quarry

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Field doesn't know

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– I don't know

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– I don't know

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– I don't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– I don't know

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– No

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Wood

– Yes

Notes: Not preserved

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– Yes

↳ Grass
– No

↳ Stone
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Other
– Other [specify]: No

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Mudbricks

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):
– Yes

↳ On the outside:
– No

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

Notes: Wall paintings

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Christ, Holy Spirit

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Apostles, Saints, Prophets

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– No

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Lion, peacock

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: No

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– Yes

Notes: Egyptian-style relief dating to the late Ptolemaic or early Roman period. The scene depicts three standing deities with hieroglyphic labels positioned between them. Existed before the occupation of the site by the monastic community.

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Yes

Notes: Capitals, stelae

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– No

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

↳ Type

– 'True' fresco

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– Yes

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: Christian iconography (Last Supper, Communion of the Apostles, the Three Hebrews in the Fiery Furnace)

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– No

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– No

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Prayers, invocations, commemorative

↳ Other type of decoration:

– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– No

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: Three cemeteries have been discovered in the area: Cemetery 1 in Wadi Sarga; Cemetery 2 in front of the church at Deir al-Ganadleh; Cemetery 3 near the village of Deir el-Ganadleh.

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– Yes

↳ Are they sky deity:

– Yes

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– No

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– Yes

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– No

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Are they other:

–Other [specify]: No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Field doesn't know

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

Notes: Liturgy, prayer

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

Notes: Holy Communion

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– No

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– No

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

–specify: Unknown

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

–specify: Unknown

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– Yes

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Yes

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Yes

↳ By all the community

– Yes

↳ By specific individuals

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– I don't know

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Field doesn't know

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– No

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– Yes

↳ Present part time

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Notes: Male

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– I don't know

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– No

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Yes

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does this place lease out land:

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Does this place lease out tools:
 - Field doesn't know

Public Works

- Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:
 - I don't know

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Yes

Notes: Medical, magical, mathematical, letters, accounts and lists, contracts, invoices, receipts.

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Yes

- ↳ Are they written:
 - Yes

- ↳ Are they written at this place:
 - Yes

- ↳ Are they oral:
 - No

- ↳ Is there a story associated with the origin and/or construction of this place:
 - No

- ↳ Are there religious specialists in charge of interpreting the scriptures:
 - Yes

- ↳ Are the scriptures part of the building/place:
 - Yes

- ↳ Attached to the structures as decoration:

– No

↳ Housed within the place/structure:

– Yes

↳ As dedicatory inscription(s):

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Inscriptions on wall paintings.

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Wadi Sarga Monastery, Thompson, R. Campbell. "Byzantine Research Fund: Excavations at Wadi Sarga" 1, no. 3 (July 1914). <https://doi.org/10.2307/3853640>.

Reference: Wadi Sarga Monastery, Dalton, O. M.. "A Coptic Wall-painting from Wadi Sarga" 3, no. 1 (January 1916). <https://doi.org/10.2307/3853590>.